

GS 80 SPHINX SW
DRIFT SECTION A
NOTES ON SAMPLES

SAMPLE NO.	COORDINATES	STRATIGRAPHIC LEVEL	DEPTH FROM SECTION FACE	GEO. UNIT	EXTRACTION DATE	TIME	LIGHT	REMARKS
SWio 1	8.18/- .10	(7)	22 cm	-	13/x1/80	3:45	SHADE	BROWN GREY SAND W. DISINTEGRATED SHALE LENSES
SWio 2	8.25/- .12		9-17 cm	BED 2 Bottom SHALE	13/x1/80	3:50	"	YELLOW SOFT SHALE - BEDROCK
SWio 3	8.05/+ .24	(6)	34-35 cm		13/x1/80	~ 4:00	"	Grey SAND
SWio 4	8.10/+ .29		20-22 cm	BED 2 Lower	13/x1/80	~ 4:00	"	BEDROCK
SWio 5	7.75/+ .54	(5)	46 cm		13/x1/80	~ 4:00	"	Grey-Brown <u>Sand</u>
SWio 6	7.83/+ .86		28 cm	BED 2	13/x1/80	~ 4:10	"	BEDROCK
SWio 7	8.00/+ 1.20	(4)	50 cm		13/x1/80	4:30	"	BROWN <u>SAND</u>
SWio 8	8.10/+ 1.15		30 cm	BED 2	13/x1/80	4:30	"	BEDROCK
SWio 9	6.04/- .20	(5)	37 cm		13/x1/80	4:40	"	BROWN SAND
SWio 10	6.04/- .26		16-17 cm	BED 1	13/x1/80	4:45	"	BEDROCK
SWio 11	6.14/+ 0.33	(4)	40 cm		13/x1/80	5:00	"	BROWN SAND
SWio 12		(1)	32 cm		14/x1/80	10:40	SUN	BROWN SAND (DAMP)
SWio 13		(3)	20-30 cm		14/x1/80	10:50	SUN	DISINTEGRATED YELLOW SHALE (DAMP)
SWio 14			18-20 cm	BED 2 UPPER PART	14/x1/80	10:50	SUN	BEDROCK